

RELATIONAL SPACE-TIME AND DE BROGLIE WAVES

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ABSTRACT. Relative motion of particles is examined in the context of relational space-time. It is shown that de Broglie waves may be derived as a representation of the coordinate maps between the rest-frames of these particles. Energy and momentum are not absolute characteristics of these particles, they are understood as parameters of the coordinate maps between their rest-frames. It is also demonstrated the position of a particle is not an absolute, it is contingent on the frame of reference used to observe the particle.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. **Relational space-time.** In this paper we consider the relative motion of material point particles in the context of relational space-time and aim to show that de Broglie waves¹ may be deduced as a representation of these point particles. In [3] Barbour examines in detail the development of relational concepts of space and time from Leibniz [11] up to and including his own work on relational formulations of dynamics [2, 4, 5]. A central point of discussion in [3] is that the uniformity of space means its points are indiscernible, which are made discernible only by the presence of “substance.”² This relational understanding of space and time supposes it is the varied and changing distribution of matter which endows space-time with enough variety to distinguish points therein.

Figure 1 illustrates point-like observers \mathcal{O}_a and \mathcal{O}_b with associated rest-frames K_a and K_b , in a state of relative motion. In the frame K_a it appears the observer \mathcal{O}_b moves between space-time locations (t_1, x_1)

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¹de Broglie waves as defined by Dirac [10] p.120

²In the sense used by Minkowski, Cologne (1908) [13]

Figure 1. The relative motion of \mathcal{O}_a and \mathcal{O}_b and the coordinate displacements this defines in the reference frames K_a and K_b .

and (t_2, x_2) , while \mathcal{O}_a “moves” between locations $(t_1, 0)$ and $(t_2, 0)$. On the other hand the observer \mathcal{O}_b is seen to “move” in its rest-frame K_b between space-time locations of the form $(\tau_{1b}, 0)$ and $(\tau_{2b}, 0)$ while \mathcal{O}_a moves between (τ_{1a}, ξ_1) and (τ_{2a}, ξ_2) . The spatial separation between the points (t_1, x_1) and (t_2, x_2) is simply not recognised in the rest frame of \mathcal{O}_b in the relational framework. On the contrary, the locations $x = x_1$ and $x = x_2$ are made discernible only because the material point \mathcal{O}_b is observed to move between these locations.

Furthermore the instants $t = t_1$ and $t = t_2$ are made discernible only by the changing location of \mathcal{O}_b with respect to \mathcal{O}_a . Indeed it is such material re-configurations which allow for the measurement of time intervals in practice. For instance, the motion of a sprinter between two fixed positions on a race-track is compared to the number of periodic vibrations of a quartz crystal, typically oscillating at 2^{15} Hz in modern watches. The relational viewpoint suggests that the instants $t = t_1$ and $t = t_2$ have no intrinsic separation (or indeed meaning) without reference to the observed motion of \mathcal{O}_b between the locations $x = x_1$ and $x = x_2$.

The distinction between instants t_1 and t_2 and the spatial locations x_1 and x_2 is made discernible only because the observer \mathcal{O}_b has been observed to move between these space-time locations. Likewise, the distinction between the locations $(\tau_{1b}, 0)$ and $(\tau_{2b}, 0)$ in K_b is made physical only because \mathcal{O}_a is observed to move between locations (τ_{1a}, ξ_1) and (τ_{2a}, ξ_2) , which are themselves made discernible in K_b only because of the observed motion of \mathcal{O}_a . In particular, it is clear that space-time locations in the frames K_a and K_b only become physically manifest by the reconfiguration of material observers \mathcal{O}_a and \mathcal{O}_b . This in turn implies that each location in $(t, x) \in K_a$ becomes physically manifest only if it has a counterpart $(\tau, \xi) \in K_b$, and vice-versa.

On the other hand, it is understood that the *coordinate differences* in each frame of reference serve to characterise the relative motion, for instance it is the coordinate difference $(t_2 - t_1, x_2 - x_1)$ which serve to define the velocity and related energy-momentum of \mathcal{O}_b with reference to K_a . It is these coordinate differences and their transformation between reference frames which contains all physical information about the system of observers \mathcal{O}_a and \mathcal{O}_b . In other words, the space-time locations labelled by K_a and K_b are not in themselves fundamental, however, the *transformation of coordinate differences* from one reference frame to another is fundamental.

1.2. Relativity and de Broglie waves. It is assumed the observer \mathcal{O}_b moves with reference to K_a at constant velocity $v = \beta c$, where $\beta \in (-1, 1)$ and c is the speed of light. The coordinate map $\Xi : K_a \rightarrow K_b$ takes the form

$$(1) \quad \tau = \gamma \left(t - \frac{\beta}{c} x \right) \quad \xi = \gamma (x - c\beta t); \quad \gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}.$$

The point emphasised by de Broglie [7, 8] is \mathcal{O}_b has an associated angular frequency

$$(2) \quad \omega_0 = \frac{E_0}{\hbar},$$

which may be obtained from the Planck and Einstein relations $E = \hbar\omega$ and $E_0 = mc^2$, where m is the rest mass of \mathcal{O}_b .

Given this angular frequency, de Broglie postulated that the wave-form $\psi(\tau, \xi) = e^{i\omega_0\tau}$ is naturally associated with the observer \mathcal{O}_b . Meanwhile (1) ensures this wave-form with respect to K_a is of the form

$$(3) \quad \psi(t, x) = e^{i\omega_0\gamma(t - \frac{\beta}{c}x)} = e^{i(\omega t - kx)},$$

where $\omega = \gamma\omega_0$ and $k = \frac{\omega_0\beta\gamma}{c} = \frac{\beta}{c}\omega$. The relativistic energy and momentum of \mathcal{O}_b with reference to K_a are given by $E = mc^2\gamma$ and $p = mc\beta\gamma$, and as such the wave-form $\psi(t, x)$ may be also written as

$$(4) \quad \psi(t, x) = e^{i(\omega t - kx)} := e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(Et - px)}.$$

Thus the relativistic energy-momentum (E, p) of the observer \mathcal{O}_b are related to the angular frequency ω and wave-number k of the associated wave-form ψ .

A point of importance for de Broglie was that the wave form $\psi(t, x)$ is always in phase with a clock of period $T_0 = \frac{2\pi}{\omega_0} = \frac{mc^2}{\hbar}$ at rest in the frame K_b . This clock is shown in Figure 2 as an oscillator moving along the y -axis of the frame K_b with angular frequency ω_0 . The period and

Figure 2. Snapshots of the relative motion of \mathcal{O}_a and \mathcal{O}_b , their local clocks with frequencies ω and ω_0 and the wave-form $\psi(t, x) = \cos(\omega t - kx)$. A related animation may be found at: [de Broglie wave animation](#)

angular frequency of this clock relative to K_a are

$$(5) \quad T = \gamma T_0 \quad \Omega = \frac{2\pi}{T} = \frac{\omega_0}{\gamma}.$$

The angular frequency Ω is not to be confused with the angular frequency of $\psi(t, x)$ which is $\omega = \gamma\omega_0$ and for reference Figure 2 also shows a similar clock at rest in K_a with angular frequency ω .

The clock co-moving with \mathcal{O}_b moving between (t, x) and $(t + dt, x + \beta c dt)$ in K_a will undergo a phase-shift $d\Phi = \Omega dt = \frac{\omega_0}{\gamma} dt$. Meanwhile, the phase difference of the wave $\psi(t, x)$, between (t, x) and $(t + dt, x + \beta c dt)$ is

$$(6) \quad \omega_0 \gamma \left(dt - \frac{\beta}{c} \beta c dt \right) = \frac{\omega_0}{\gamma} dt = d\Phi,$$

so the moving clock and wave-form $\psi(t, x)$ are in phase, see Figure 2. It is clear then that de Broglie waves are closely connected with the Lorentz transformation between local inertial reference frames K_a and K_b , in particular with the coordinate map $\tau(t, x)$. The aim now is derive the existence of such a wave-form as a representation of this coordinate map between the rest-frames of the observers \mathcal{O}_a and \mathcal{O}_b .

2. COORDINATE MAPS AND THEIR GOVERNING EQUATIONS

2.1. Motion and coordinate maps. At any instant of its motion through K_a , the observer \mathcal{O}_b is following a trajectory with tangent vector (dt, dx) , while the corresponding trajectory with reference to K_b is of the form $(d\tau, 0)$. Correspondingly, the observer \mathcal{O}_a must be travelling along a trajectory in K_b whose tangent vector is of the form $(d\tau, d\xi)$, while this tangent vector has counterpart $(dt, 0)$ with reference to K_a , cf. Figure 1.

In general, coordinate differences $(d\tau, d\xi)$ with reference to K_b are related to their counterparts (dt, dx) with reference to K_a according to

$$\begin{bmatrix} d\tau \\ d\xi \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_t & \tau_x \\ \xi_t & \xi_x \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} dt \\ dx \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{bmatrix} dt \\ dx \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} t_\tau & t_\xi \\ x_\tau & x_\xi \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} d\tau \\ d\xi \end{bmatrix},$$

where sub-scripts denote differentiation with respect to the relevant variable. To ensure consistency with the special theory of relativity, it is required that tangent vectors of the form $(dt, \beta c dt)$, $(dt, 0)$ and

$(dt, c dt)$ have counterparts $(d\tau, 0)$, $(d\tau, -\beta c d\tau)$ and $(d\tau, c d\tau)$ respectively. This requires the Jacobian matrices of the coordinate maps to be of the form

$$(7) \quad \begin{bmatrix} d\tau \\ d\xi \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_t & \tau_x \\ c^2 \tau_x & \tau_t \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} dt \\ dx \end{bmatrix} \iff \begin{bmatrix} dt \\ dx \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} t_\tau & \frac{1}{c^2} x_\tau \\ x_\tau & t_\tau \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} d\tau \\ d\xi \end{bmatrix},$$

In addition it is required that the Jacobian of each coordinate map should satisfy

$$(8) \quad J = \tau_t^2 - c^2 \tau_x^2 = t_\tau^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} x_\tau^2 = 1$$

2.2. The Hamilton-Jacobi Equations. The action for the coordinate map $\mathbf{X} : K_b \rightarrow K_a$, associated with the motion $(t_1, x_1) \rightarrow (t, x)$ induced by the motion of \mathcal{O}_b along the corresponding trajectory $(\tau_1, 0) \rightarrow (\tau, 0)$ is given by

$$(9) \quad S[\underline{x}] = \frac{E_0}{2c^2} \int_{\tau_1}^{\tau} \underline{x}_\tau \cdot \underline{x}_\tau d\tau = \int_{\tau_1}^{\tau} L[\underline{x}, \underline{x}_\tau] d\tau.$$

The notation means $\underline{x}(\tau) \equiv (ct(\tau, 0), x(\tau, 0)) \in K_a$ which is the image of the map $\mathbf{X} : K_b \rightarrow K_a$ applied to the trajectory $\underline{\xi}(\tau) \equiv (\tau, 0) \in K_b$. The inner-product is given by

$$\underline{x}_\tau \cdot \underline{x}_\tau = c^2 t_\tau^2 - x_\tau^2 = c^2 J$$

where J is the Jacobian of the coordinate map $\mathbf{X} : K_b \rightarrow K_a$ (cf. equation (8)). The constraint $J = 1$ is interpreted as a weak equation, to be applied *after* variational derivatives are calculated, in line with the terminology of Dirac (cf. [9]).

Under a variation of the form $\underline{x}(\tau) \rightarrow \underline{x}(\tau) + \epsilon \underline{u}(\tau)$, Hamilton's principle is simply the requirement $\frac{d}{d\epsilon} S[\underline{x} + \epsilon \underline{u}]|_{\epsilon=0} = 0$, and can be written for a general Lagrangian $L[\underline{x}, \underline{x}_\tau]$ according to

$$(10) \quad \int_{\tau_1}^{\tau} \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial \underline{x}} - \frac{d}{d\tau} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \underline{x}_\tau} \right] \cdot \underline{u} d\tau + \int_{\tau_1}^{\tau} \frac{d}{d\tau} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \underline{x}_\tau} \cdot \underline{u} \right) d\tau = 0$$

after integration by parts. Imposing the boundary conditions $\underline{u}(\tau_1) = \underline{u}(\tau_b) = \underline{0}$ to an otherwise arbitrary variation $\underline{u}(\tau)$, yields the Euler-Lagrange equations

$$(11) \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial \underline{x}} - \frac{d}{d\tau} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \underline{x}_\tau} = \underline{0}.$$

When $L = \frac{E_0}{2c^2} (c^2 t_\tau^2 - x_\tau^2)$ specifically, the Euler-Lagrange equations for the coordinate map $\mathbf{X} : K_b \rightarrow K_a$ satisfies $\frac{d^2}{d\tau^2} \mathbf{X}(\tau, 0) = 0$.

The Hamilton-Jacobi equation follow from the condition $\underline{x}(\tau)$ is a physical path (i.e. satisfying (11)), while the variation is now required to satisfy $\underline{u}(\tau_1) = \underline{0}$ only, while $\underline{u}(\tau)$ may be arbitrarily chosen. The variation of the action under this perturbation is obtained from (10)

$$(12) \quad \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{S[\underline{x} + \epsilon \underline{u}] - S[\underline{x}]}{\epsilon \underline{u}} = \frac{\partial S}{\partial \underline{x}} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \underline{x}_\tau}.$$

The canonical energy-momentum associated with the trajectory of \mathcal{O}_b , with reference to the frame K_a , is given by

$$(13) \quad \begin{cases} \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = E_p = E_0 t_\tau \implies t_\tau = \frac{E_p}{E_0} \\ \frac{\partial S}{\partial x} = -p = \frac{E_0}{c^2} x_\tau \implies x_\tau = \frac{c^2 p}{E_0} \end{cases}$$

The Hamiltonian associated with coordinate map $\mathbf{X} : K_b \rightarrow K_a$ along $(\tau, 0)$ is

$$H = \underline{p} \cdot \underline{x}_\tau - L = \frac{E_p^2 - c^2 p^2}{2E_0},$$

which of course is conserved.

Upon imposing the constraint $J = 1$, it follows that

$$(14) \quad \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} \right)^2 - c^2 \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial x} \right)^2 = E_0^2.$$

Conservation of energy-momentum in the form $\frac{1}{c^2} \partial_t E_p + \partial_x p = 0$ or equivalently

$$(15) \quad \frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial t^2} - c^2 \frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial x^2} = 0,$$

is consistent with this constraint, since $\partial_t \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = \partial_t \frac{\partial L}{\partial t_\tau} = \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial t \partial t_\tau} = 0$ and likewise for $\frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial x^2}$.

Upon using the relations (13) and the constraint (14), we also find

$$(16) \quad \frac{dS}{d\tau} = \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} t_\tau + \frac{\partial S}{\partial x} \cdot x_\tau = E_0,$$

and so integrating with respect to τ yields $S[\underline{x}] = E_0\tau(\underline{x})$ up to an additive constant. Given $S[\underline{x}] = E_0\tau(\underline{x})$, it follows the system (14)–(15) governing the action $S[t, x]$ also governs the component $\tau(t, x)$ of the coordinate map $\Xi : K_a \rightarrow K_b$, which similarly satisfies

$$(17a) \quad \partial_t^2 \tau - c^2 \partial_x^2 \tau = 0$$

$$(17b) \quad (\partial_t \tau)^2 - c^2 (\partial_x \tau)^2 = 1.$$

Solutions of the system (17a)–(17b) will form representations of the coordinate map $\tau(t, x)$.

3. COORDINATE MAPS AND THEIR REPRESENTATIONS

3.1. Linearity of the coordinate maps. The main result of this section is that the system (14)–(15) only admits solutions $S[t, x]$ which are linear in t and x . However, it will also be shown that S as a solution of (17a)–(17b) may be represented as an exponential function of t and x (cf. [14]).

Without imposing assumptions or restrictions, we consider a general solution of the form

$$(18) \quad S(t, x) = E_0 \Theta(\psi(t, x)),$$

where $\Theta(\psi(t, x)) = \tau(t, x)$ with $\psi(t, x)$ being a representation of $\tau(t, x)$. Substituting (18) into the governing equations (14)–(15) yields

$$(19a) \quad [\partial_t^2 \psi - c^2 \partial_x^2 \psi] \Theta'(\psi) + [(\partial_t \psi)^2 - c^2 (\partial_x \psi)^2] \Theta''(\psi) = 0$$

$$(19b) \quad [(\partial_t \psi)^2 - c^2 (\partial_x \psi)^2] \Theta'(\psi)^2 = 1,$$

where $\Theta'(\psi) = \frac{d\Theta}{d\psi}$.

Equation (19b) applied to equation (19a) now yields

$$(20) \quad \partial_t^2 \psi - c^2 \partial_x^2 \psi + \frac{\Theta''(\psi)}{\Theta'(\psi)^3} = 0.$$

Multiplying by $\partial_t \psi$, it now follows that

$$(21) \quad \frac{1}{2} \partial_t \left[(\partial_t \psi)^2 - \frac{1}{\Theta'(\psi)^2} \right] - c^2 \partial_x^2 \psi \partial_t \psi = 0,$$

while substituting from equation (19b) we deduce

$$\partial_x \psi \partial_x \partial_t \psi - \partial_t \psi \partial_x^2 \psi = 0$$

from which it follows $\partial_x \left(\frac{\partial_x \psi}{\partial_t \psi} \right) = 0$. Multiplying equation (20) by $\partial_x \psi$ we also deduce $\partial_t \left(\frac{\partial_x \psi}{\partial_t \psi} \right) = 0$, and as such $\frac{\partial_x \psi}{\partial_t \psi}$ is constant.

This means the functions $\partial_t \psi$ and $\partial_x \psi$ are linearly dependent. It follows that ψ may be written according to

$$\psi(t, x) = \phi(\omega t - kx) \implies \frac{\partial_x \psi}{\partial_t \psi} = -\frac{k}{\omega},$$

where $\phi(\cdot)$ is yet to be determined while ω and k are constants. The constraint (17b) or equivalently (19b) now requires

$$(22) \quad \left(\omega_0 \frac{d\phi}{ds} \frac{d\Theta}{d\phi} \right)^2 = 1, \quad \omega_0^2 = \omega^2 - c^2 k^2 > 0,$$

where we introduce $s = \omega t - kx$. Taking the square-root of (22) we now have $\pm \omega_0 \frac{d\phi}{ds} \frac{d\Theta}{d\phi} = 1$ and so integrating it follows that $\Theta(\phi(s)) = \pm \frac{s}{\omega_0}$, or equivalently

$$(23) \quad \tau(t, x) = \Theta(\psi(t, x)) = \pm \frac{\omega t - kx}{\omega_0}.$$

Formally, we have applied the inverse function theorem to equation (22) which ensures $\pm \omega_0 \Theta(\cdot) = \phi^{-1}(\cdot)$ (see [18] for instance). It also follows from (13) and (23) with $S = E_0 \tau$ that

$$(24) \quad \begin{cases} \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = E \implies \frac{\omega}{\omega_0} = \frac{E}{E_0} \\ \frac{\partial S}{\partial x} = -p \implies \frac{k}{\omega_0} = \frac{p}{E_0}. \end{cases}$$

3.2. Representations of the coordinate map. As a functional equation for $\Theta(\phi)$, we note that under the re-scaling $\phi \rightarrow r\phi$ for a non-zero constant r , equation (22) also requires

$$(25) \quad r^2 \Theta'(r\phi)^2 \dot{\phi}(s)^2 = \Theta'(\phi)^2 \dot{\phi}(s)^2 = 1.$$

It follows $r^2\Theta'(r\phi)^2$ is independent of r and so $\Theta'(r\phi) \propto \frac{1}{r\phi}$ from which it follows

$$(26) \quad E_0\Theta(\psi(t, x)) = \alpha \ln \psi = \pm E_0 \frac{\omega t - kx}{\omega_0},$$

where α is a constant action parameter. The representation $\psi(t, x)$ of the coordinate map $\tau(t, x)$ is now explicitly:

$$(27) \quad \psi(t, x) = e^{\pm \frac{1}{\alpha}(Et - px)},$$

having used equation (24) to re-write the ratios $\frac{E_0\omega}{\omega_0} = E$ and $\frac{E_0k}{\omega_0} = p$.

The other possible solution of (22) is simply

$$(28) \quad \left. \begin{array}{l} \phi(s) = \kappa s \\ \omega_0\Theta(\phi) = \pm \frac{\phi}{\kappa} \end{array} \right\} \implies \Theta(\phi(s)) = \pm \frac{s}{\omega_0}$$

where κ is constant, thereby ensuring $\frac{d^2\phi}{ds^2} = 0$ and $\frac{d^2\Theta}{d\phi^2} = 0$. This in turn ensures (19a) is satisfied while (19b) is satisfied by definition of ω_0 and s .

3.3. Momentum measurement & de Broglie waves. In §§3.1–3.2

it has been shown that the coordinate map $S = E_0\tau(t, x)$ governed by (17b)–(17a), is necessarily linear $E_0\tau(t, x) = \pm(Et - px)$ and has a representation of the form $E_0\tau(t, x) = \alpha \ln \psi(t, x)$. Combining these observations then it is necessary that the representation $\psi(t, x)$ is of the form

$$\psi(t, x) = \exp\left\{\pm \frac{1}{\alpha}(Et - kx)\right\}.$$

It is already clear α must have the units of action, so the choice \hbar is obvious. To ensure the representation $\psi(t, x)$ corresponds to a de Broglie wave of the form (4), it is also necessary to show α is imaginary, which is the aim of the current section.

Figure 3 shows a very simple apparatus consisting of two massive plates \mathcal{P}_l and \mathcal{P}_r , both initially static at $x_l = 0$ and $x_r = \lambda$ with reference to the frame K , with rest energy \mathcal{E}_0 each. It is supposed the point-like observer \mathcal{O}_b is located at some $x \in (x_l, x_r)$, and interacts with either plate only by collision. Upon collision \mathcal{O}_b undergoes a change

of momentum, thereby imparting momentum to one of these plates. Measurement of momentum means \mathcal{O}_b impacts one of the plates and

Figure 3. The measurement of \mathcal{O}_b 's momentum by collision with massive plates of equal rest-energy \mathcal{E}_0 .

sets it in motion relative to the other. Immediately after impact the plates are again inertial observers, since there is no further interaction to impart momentum to either plate.

If $K_l \ni (t', x')$ denotes the rest-frame of \mathcal{P}_l , then its coordinates with reference to this frame will always be of the form $(t', 0)$; those of \mathcal{P}_r will be of the form (t', λ) prior to collision. Similarly, $K_r \ni (t^*, x^*)$ is the rest-frame of \mathcal{P}_r whose coordinates are always of the form $(t^*, 0)$; those of \mathcal{P}_l are of the form $(t^*, -\lambda)$ initially. Prior to collision it makes sense to identify coordinates $(t, x) \in K$, $(t', x') \in K_l$ and $(t^*, x^*) \in K_r$ since all three frames see the observers \mathcal{P}_l and \mathcal{P}_r at rest, and so all are equivalent up to constant translations.

At the moment of measurement as observed from the frame K_l , it appears the observer \mathcal{P}_r changes energy-momentum according to $(\mathcal{E}_0, 0) \rightarrow (\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{P})$ where $\mathcal{E}^2 = \mathcal{P}^2 c^2 + \mathcal{E}_0^2$ and $\mathcal{P} > 0$ is assumed. Meanwhile the momentum of \mathcal{O}_b changes according to $(E, p) \rightarrow (E_1, p - \mathcal{P})$ (cf. Figure 3). Naturally, the energy-momentum of \mathcal{P}_l is *always* $(\mathcal{E}_0, 0)$ in the frame K_l while the observer \mathcal{O}_b is interpreted to occupy the location $x' = \lambda$ upon collision. Conversely, in the frame K_r the observer \mathcal{P}_l changes its energy-momentum according to $(\mathcal{E}_0, 0) \rightarrow (\mathcal{E}, -\mathcal{P})$ and the energy-momentum of \mathcal{O}_b changes according to $(E, -p) \rightarrow (E_1, -p + \mathcal{P})$.

In this frame of reference the observer \mathcal{O}_b is interpreted to appear at $x^* = -\lambda$ upon impact, and by definition the energy-momentum of \mathcal{P}_r is *always* $(\mathcal{E}_0, 0)$.

Given that \mathcal{P}_l and \mathcal{P}_r are in uniform relative motion before and after collision with \mathcal{O}_b , it follows from §3.2 the component $t^*(t', x')$ of the coordinate map $\mathbf{X}^* : K_l \rightarrow K_r$ has representation

$$\psi(t', x') = \begin{cases} e^{\frac{1}{\alpha}\mathcal{E}_0(t'-t'_0)}, & t' < t'_0 \\ e^{\frac{1}{\alpha}(\mathcal{E}(t'-t'_0) - \mathcal{P}x')} & t' \geq t'_0 \end{cases}$$

where the impact occurs at time t'_0 with reference to K_l . Upon impact the proper-time t^* of the observer \mathcal{P}_r changes according to

$$\frac{\alpha}{\mathcal{E}_0} \ln e^{\frac{1}{\alpha}\mathcal{E}_0(t'-t'_0)} \rightarrow \frac{\alpha}{\mathcal{E}_0} \ln e^{\frac{1}{\alpha}(\mathcal{E}(t'-t'_0) - \mathcal{P}x')},$$

from the perspective of the observer \mathcal{P}_l . However, according to the observer \mathcal{P}_r its own time coordinate is continuous, while it is the time coordinate of \mathcal{P}_l which undergoes a corresponding change during collision with \mathcal{O}_b . Continuity of the t^* -coordinate now requires

$$(29) \quad \lim_{t' \rightarrow t'_0} e^{\frac{1}{\alpha}\mathcal{E}_0(t'-t'_0)} = \lim_{t' \rightarrow t'_0} e^{\frac{1}{\alpha}(\mathcal{E}(t'-t'_0) - \mathcal{P}\lambda)} \iff e^{-\frac{\mathcal{P}\lambda}{\alpha}} = 1.$$

Since $\lambda \neq 0$ and $\mathcal{P} > 0$ by assumption, continuity of $\psi(t, x)$ at t'_0 is satisfied only when the argument of the exponential is of the form $2\pi ni$ for $n \in \mathbb{Z}$. Hence, we deduce

$$\alpha = -i\hbar, \quad \mathcal{P} = \frac{2\pi n\hbar}{\lambda},$$

and so the action parameter α is imaginary as anticipated.

With $\alpha = -i\hbar$ it is now clear that the coordinate transformation between the rest frames of inertial observers may be represented by wave-forms

$$(30) \quad \psi(t, x) = e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(E_p t - p x)},$$

whose eigenvalues may be defined as

$$(31) \quad E_p = \bar{\psi}(-i\hbar\partial_t)\psi \quad p = \bar{\psi}(i\hbar\partial_x)\psi,$$

where $\bar{\psi}$ denotes the complex conjugate of ψ . Both representations ψ and $\bar{\psi}$ satisfy the Klein-Gordon equation

$$(32) \quad \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \psi = 0.$$

Thus, de Broglie waves as per Dirac's terminology (see [10], p. 120) emerge as a representation of the τ -component of the coordinate map $\Xi : K_a \rightarrow K_b$, and so represents to trajectory of \mathcal{O}_b (i.e. $(\tau, 0) \in K_b$ with reference to K_a).

The existence of de Broglie waves was confirmed almost immediately after de Broglie's first prediction [7], with the interference experiments of Davisson & Germer [6] and the contemporaneous experiments of Thomson & Reid [21]. In the years since, the experimental evidence supporting de Broglie's conjecture has accumulated steadily (see [1, 19, 20] among others).

3.4. Energy-momentum eigenfunctions. The τ -representation given in equation (30) is an eigenfunction of the linear operators $-i\hbar\partial_t$ and $i\hbar\partial_x$, whose corresponding eigenvalues are simply the energy-momentum of the observer \mathcal{O}_b with reference to the frame K_a . The nonlinear constraint (17b) has a particularly elegant geometric interpretation in the relational context, since one may reformulate the coordinate map (7) according to

$$(33) \quad \begin{bmatrix} d\tau \\ d\xi \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_t & \tau_x \\ \xi_t & \xi_x \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} dt \\ dx \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_t & \tau_x \\ c^2\tau_x & \tau_t \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} dt \\ dx \end{bmatrix}$$

in which case $\tau_t^2 - c^2\tau_x^2 = 1$ is equivalent to $\det \begin{bmatrix} \tau_t & \tau_x \\ \xi_t & \xi_x \end{bmatrix} = 1$.

Hence, the Jacobian of the coordinate transformation $\Xi : K_a \rightarrow K_b$ is required to be one, thus ensuring this map is invertible. Specifically, it means that a trajectory (dt, dx) in K_a has as counterpart $(d\tau, d\xi)$ with reference to K_b and vice-versa. In particular it means that a trajectory of \mathcal{O}_b in K_b given by $(d\tau, 0)$ has a counterpart (dt, dx) in K_a , while simultaneously the trajectory of \mathcal{O}_a in K_a given by $(dt, 0)$

has a counterpart $(d\tau, d\xi)$ in K_b , cf. Figure 1. As such, these observers appear as point-like bodies moving with reference to the rest-frame of their counterpart (cf. Figure 1). This is only possible since the conditions (17a)–(17b) are both satisfied for the coordinate map $E_0\tau(t, x) = -i\hbar \ln \psi(t, x)$ when $\psi(t, x)$ is an energy-momentum eigenfunction.

Contrarily, given the linearity of (32) it is clear that superpositions of the form $\varphi(t, x) = \iint \delta(E^2 - E_p^2) a(E, p) e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(Et - px)} dE dp$ are also valid solutions of this wave equation. Such a superposition cannot represent a physically realisable coordinate map from K_a to K_b since the non-linear constraint (17b) is not satisfied for $-i\hbar \ln \varphi$. This is not to say \mathcal{O}_b becomes somehow de-localised, it always has a precise location $(\tau, 0) \in K_b$. Rather, it is the case there is no longer a precise correspondence of the form (7) between the frames K_a and K_b , and so the trajectory $(d\tau, 0)$ in K_b no longer has a precise counterpart with reference to K_a satisfying all the required axioms of special relativity.

4. DISCUSSION

A central point of the argument in §3.3 is that the observers \mathcal{P}_l and \mathcal{P}_r are both always inertial in their own rest-frames, and the acceleration of the pair upon impact with \mathcal{O}_b is only defined in relative terms. This is apparently consistent only in the relational space-time framework. Moreover, the derivation presented here appears to be consistent with Rovelli’s Relational Quantum Mechanics (RQM) [15, 17], whereby the properties of a system are not absolutes. In particular, the perceived location and momentum of \mathcal{O}_b upon impact with the apparatus depends on the frame of reference adopted for the measurement.

Indeed the physical properties of a system, in this case the energy-momentum of \mathcal{P}_l and \mathcal{P}_r , is a characteristic of interaction between the observers, specifically it is a property of the coordinate maps between their respective rest-frames (cf. [12]). It is also clear the observer \mathcal{O}_b does not have an *absolute location* in this experiment, its apparent

location is contingent on the frame of reference used for the observation. Thus the derivation presented here also appears to lend support to Rovelli's hypothesis (see [16] pp. 220–221) that the relational character of states in RQM is connected to the relational framework of space and time.

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